

**POWER OF PBL IN DEVELOPING
PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS' SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING**

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Abstract :

This study aims to find out how students feel about the impact of problem-based learning primarily on the development of self-directed learning and academic achievement. The subjects of this study were fifth semester students (18 students) who were studying the “Teaching Learning Strategy” subject matter from Faculty of Islamic Studies, Islamic University of Jakarta. The method used in this study was a qualitative approach based on surveys and descriptive explanatory, so the techniques of data collection used deep observation and deep interview. The result of the data analysis showed that the students who were taught with the application of PBL strategy increased the quality of their teaching and learning process and learning achievement significantly. In learning processed students showed that they were eager to study, because they knew what they wanted to learn and they were doing it with pleasure and joy. All of the students felt satisfied with PBL, and they ask to do it again in another course. They realized this PBL strategy they will use after they teach later in school and they have already known that their students will be happy with PBL as they were also happy with it.

Keywords: Problem-based learning, self-directed learning, academic achievement, learning outcomes

Introduction

According to Duch, Groch and Allen (2003), the past decade has seen major changes in how to communicate, do business, access information, and use technology. The way we learn must also change in order to prepare our students to deal with these new situations: Students need more than ever before to be able to ask questions, find and find the right resources to answer these questions, and inform others about their solutions effectively. Problem-based learning is an instructional strategy that helps students build the thinking and communication skills necessary to succeed today. Particularly for potential teachers, by implicating PBL in their courses, there is much to be gained, among other things; they will have experience of how the steps in delivering a subject using PBL, later if they teach in high school, they can apply Immediately PBL in presenting the subject, coupled with self-directed learning develops without realizing it, are bolder in candid opinions, more patient in listening to his friend's opinion, they can appreciate the opinions of others, and can determine their own goals that they will achieve, and how to achieve them effectively.

Presentation of literature

Problem-based learning enhances the ability to identify information needed for a particular application, where and how to search for that information, how to organize that information into a meaningful conceptual framework, and how to communicate that information to others. The use of collaborative workgroups promotes the development of learning communities in all classrooms, enhancing student achievement (Johnson, Johnson, Smith, 1991). Moreover, Wilkerson and Gijsselaers (1996) claimed that PBL characterized a student-centered approach, teachers “facilitators rather than publishers”, and open problems (in PBL, called “disorganized”) as the primary motivation and framework for learning ”(p. 101 In addition to all the characteristics described above, the PBL requires students to be knowledgeable about the subject (PBL) .102) Trainers also hope to develop students' substantive interest in the subject, emphasize learning rather than reminders, encourage teamwork, and help students become self-taught. In other words, students must learn to be aware of the information they know For about the problem, and the

information you need to know to solve the problem, and the strategies that should be used to solve the problem. Help the ability to express these ideas students to become more effective in solving problems and self-educated mentors.

However, there are educational practices that help to develop such skills without abandoning the content. Quoting John Dewey's observation that "true learning is based on discovery guided by guidance rather than knowledge transfer" (Boyer, 1998). In line with this, student-centered education, especially problem-based education, is in line with this philosophy. The basic principle that supports the concept of PBL is older than formal education itself; any learning begins with a problem, query or puzzle that the learner wants to solve (Boud & Feletti, 1991). According to Duch and Groch and Allen (2003), problem-based learning directly addresses many of the recommended and desirable outcomes of university education: specifically, the ability to think critically and the ability to analyze and solve complex real-world problems. Find, evaluate and use appropriate learning resources to work collaboratively in small teams and groups, to demonstrate versatile and effective communication skills, verbal and written, and to use content knowledge and intellectual skills acquired at the university to become permanent learners

Self-directed Learning and Problem-Based Learning

According to Malcolm Knowles (1975, p. 18), self-learning describes "the process by which individuals take the initiative, with or without the help of others, in diagnosing their educational needs, formulating learning objectives, and identifying human and material resources in order to say Hiemstra, R. In essence, self-directed learning is seen as any form of study in which individuals take primary responsibility for planning, implementing, and even evaluating effort. Furthermore, Briggs (2015) strongly agrees with Knowles and says it is a particularly important concept in climate. Current tutorial, before long, we will learn digital decals instead of drawers When this happens, self-directed learning will be critical to the skills of any student hoping to succeed, according to Wilcox and Susan (1996), a clear focus on student learning in adult education provides a valuable and distinctive perspective for teachers committed to providing Effective education in the university environment - especially those who define effective education in terms of the quality of student learning. More specifically, the focus of self-learning on personal autonomy, personal responsibility and personal growth embodies some of the most important principles of higher education and teacher education.

Boud (1988) notes that higher education and adult education share a common interest in order to develop student responsibility and independence in learning. Similarly, Knapper & Cropley (1991) suggests that the principles of adult learning and lifelong learning should be adopted in higher education institutions, because students will continue to use lifelong learning skills long after graduation. Brookfield (1990) and Cranton (1989, 1992) have clearly demonstrated that approaches to adult student education are fully applicable at university or college. Lam (1985) studied the learning experiences of university students and community colleges and found that the majority of learners expressed a desire for greater partnership in the planning, organization, delivery and evaluation of courses, as advocated by the higher education literature. Finally, a specific intersection of the perspective of adult education and the preparation of higher education can be found in the philosophy and practice of problem-based education in university vocational schools (Boud & Feletti, 1991; Woods, 1994). In fact, the basic assumption of many people promoting problem-based learning is that it encourages self-directed learning in students (Ryan, 1993). In line with this Bruniges (2015) states that pedagogy in the 21st century should emphasize 4C - cooperation, critical thinking, creativity and communication, because in our rapidly changing world, the same knowledge and skills will not address future challenges. To achieve this goal, teachers must be more creative in choosing teaching and learning strategies, according to Sole (2015), PBL is one of the most suitable strategies to achieve 4 Cs. At PBL, self-directed learning can be developed by bringing prospective teachers directly to high school, observing and interviewing teachers, and they will find real problems that teachers face in their education. Potential teachers design a solution based on their research, investigation and analysis, reflecting their understanding. All activities they perform in a group include collaboration between students. At the end of the PBL steps, prospective teachers must submit their research report to their classmate. By taking into account the steps in the PBL, we can see a clearly visible process for the development of students' self-learning.

Steps Toward Self-Directed Learning

How to be self-directed learners? Briggs (2015) says she covered some background and benefits associated with self-directed learning. She shows some steps to achieve this, among other things; 1. Set your own learning goals, and you can't achieve what you never imagined. Determine what you want to learn is the first step of the process, 2.

Ask about the importance of things. He used to not take things at face value and would start asking questions because you already care about the answer, 3. Look for interesting challenges. Who says that challenges are by definition unpleasant? Identify the problem you're interested in and reward you by solving it. That's what real learning is about, 4. Monitor your learning process. Learning is more fun when you set your own criteria. Whether or not you receive the grade you want, try to measure your progress according to your personal learning goals, 5. Understand your approach. Many of us assume that we know our learning style and preferences, but do we really? Stop for a moment to think about the shape or medium that helps you learn better, 6. Develop self-motivation. The intrinsic motivation does not naturally come to everyone, but it can be learned. Help yourself to enjoy learning more by gathering interesting facts or planning to share your information with other people, 7. Share your learning with peers and mentors. Knowing that you will share what you have learned with someone else can make a big difference when it comes to learning. Both your attention and memory receive a boost when you film yourself by transferring new material to someone else. 8. Create something from what you've learned. Get used to creating something - a sketch, a song, a journal entry - with new materials you've learned. Not only will it help you to consolidate the material in your long-term memory, but it will also help you look forward to future learning endeavors. 9. Follow-up knowledge, not good grades. Grades are hard to ignore when they seem to mean a lot to university admissions staff. But it's important to keep in mind that it's not the end for everyone. Estimates do not always reflect how much you have already learned, and that is what matters in the end. 10. Check your achievements. It's one thing to know what you've learned; it's another thing to make it known. Achieving your accomplishments can be very rewarding, and can help you think about what you think you have learned versus what you have already learned. 11. Build a network of "learning colleagues". We are educated by nature. Take advantage of online and personal communities that will support you during your educational journey and help shed light on your way.

Research question: This study attempts to explore how students feel about the impact of problem-based learning on the development of self-learning and academic achievement.

In data collection in two ways through observation and in-depth interview. For observation conducted during the semester which is 6 times using PBL. In the first session, the lecturer describes the course of the "Learning and Teaching Strategy" as well as the PBL steps that will be implemented in the teaching and learning process. Students are then divided into four groups, two groups of 5 students and two other groups of 4 students. Each group was assigned to visit a secondary school to conduct a survey on any difficulties teachers face in delivering materials in the classroom. To conduct the survey, prospective teachers were provided with interview guidelines. The results of the school survey were reported in front of the class, and then discussed which led to the identification of the

problem and the formulation of the problem for each group. The problem they face is a real problem and an unorganized problem where the solution is not just a solution, but can be several.

When looking for solutions to problems that have already been discovered, students discuss them in their respective groups. In addition, the researcher made observations while students were working in groups. During the first group meetings, all group leaders played an active role, explaining what they should do in six sessions, and the final outcome they had to achieve. After knowing what to achieve and what to do to achieve it, each group member 2 and group 4 play an active role in communicating their ideas, while in the first group there is a student who is still silent and has not released his opinion, he just carefully watched what each of his friends said. The group leader asked the silent student about his idea, and he replied "Not yet" until the first meeting ended and remained silent. In Group 3, there is a less active Taliban in the discussion, with one student expressing his opinion only and the other asking the question "How do we get to the end result?" These three students are still hard to express their opinions and still feel ashamed and distrustful, so they cannot play an active role in group discussions.

At the second meeting, it was very surprising that each of the four groups played an active role. The three students who are less active, shy and less confident at the first meeting, now have an active role in the group. They can express their opinions and ask questions in the discussion. They seem to really enjoy working in groups. This continues until all six sessions. At the last meeting, each student was interviewed.

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result

From the interview data obtained as follows: With problem-based learning (PBL) we were trained to develop our knowledge and develop problem-solving skills. In addition, by providing real problems, we can shape the meaning of the lesson material through the learning process and store it in our memory so that we can use it again at any time.

We believe this strategy is one of the difficult strategies to use real-world problems as a context for learners to learn about critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

The advantages of PBL strategy are:

We feel that PBL strategy gives some advantages some other things; is a good technique to understand the content of the lesson, problems can challenge ability and give satisfaction to find new knowledge, improve learning activities, develop critical thinking ability.

4. Troubleshooting can help how to transfer knowledge to understand real life problems.

5. Problem-solving can develop the ability to think critically and develop the ability to adapt to new knowledge.

6. Problem-solving can provide an opportunity to apply existing knowledge in the real world.

I get a lot of benefits from PB strategies, namely:

- 1. I can fight to see what I don't know yet.

- 2. Determine what I need to learn

- 3. Develop awareness and encouragement to learn from within myself and seek knowledge independently.

- 4. I learned a lot in depth, so that the concepts are stored in my memory.

- 5. I have the opportunity to develop myself.

We feel that PBL strategy gives some advantages some other things; is a good technique to understand the content of the lesson, problems can challenge ability and give satisfaction to find new knowledge, improve learning activities, develop critical thinking ability. To develop self-learning, I can find it difficult to know what I do not know yet, determine what I need to learn, develop awareness and encouragement to learn from within myself, seek knowledge independently, I have the opportunity to develop myself.

Research Methodology

This research is qualitative research. Depending on how they are obtained, data can be grouped into two types, primary data and secondary data. Preliminary data are data collected, processed and presented by researchers who have obtained and collected directly from informants through observation, field observations and interviews. The secondary data outside the primary data in this case are in the form of manuscripts or written documents. Data collection techniques implemented by participatory observation, interview and documentation. Data analysis steps are performed through data submission, data reduction, classification, synthesis, and synthesis of business hypotheses.

This research uses qualitative descriptive techniques, and Bogdan and Taylor define "qualitative methods" as research procedures that produce metadata in the form of written or verbal words about observable behavior. This approach is directed towards the background and the individual wholly or properly. Therefore, in this case individuals or organizations may not be isolated to variables or hypotheses, but they should be seen as part of the whole, according to Nana Sudjana and Ibrahim, the data obtained from qualitative research are the result of observations, interviews and results of photographs, written excerpts From field documents and observations collected by researchers on the research site are not statistically mentioned, researchers immediately analyze the data by enriching the information.

This study aims to describe the application of PBL and its implications for students' self-learning. In this context, the researcher understands the process using an emotional perception perspective, which according to Mulong is a method that tries to understand a phenomenon starting from a deep point (internal or local)). In this regard, the appropriate qualitative research methodology for use in this research activity is natural phenomena. Thus,

data collection from this qualitative study was carried out (1) in normal conditions, (2) primary and secondary data sources, (3) more data collection techniques on participant observation, interviews, and documentation.

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